

EFFECTIVENESS OF MODULAR DISTANCE INSTRUCTION IN TEACHING INTRODUCTION TO THE PHILOSOPHY OF THE HUMAN PERSON

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Abstract. This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of modular distance instruction in teaching Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) in Introduction to Philosophy of the Human Person in PHINMA University of Pangasinan (UPang) College Urdaneta Inc. during the school year 2021-2022. The research was experimental. This study made use of the Quasi-Experimental Method using the two-group design. Both groups were pre-tested, and both were post-tested, the ultimate difference being that one group had undergone online distance instruction which was the control group. On the other hand, the other group was administered through modular distance instruction which was the experimental group. It employed this approach to find out the performance levels of 12 HUMSS learners using the two-delivery approach in Introduction to Philosophy of the Human Person. The performance of the control and experimental groups is low. There is a significant difference in the performance of the control and experimental groups as revealed in the post-test results. The performance of the experimental group is higher than the control group in the post-test results. There is a significant difference in the performance of the control and the experimental group in the post-test; the learners who were taught using the modular distance instruction (the experimental group) performed significantly better than the learners exposed to Online Distance Instruction (the control group) and it is concluded that the modular distance instruction is an effective teaching approach that could be used in teaching Grade 12 Introduction to Philosophy of The Human Person. The experimental group performed significantly better than the control group.

Keywords. Philosophy Human Nature, Performance Level, Module Distance Instruction, Online Distance Instruction

1 Introduction

The Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic wreaked havoc on the world in unimaginable ways. Looking back over the last two years and the devastating effects of the pandemic that continues to this day, it is clear that education was one of the hardest-hit sectors. The world, as well as educational institutions, were not prepared to embrace the rapid shift to online platforms.

COVID-19 was first identified in Wuhan City, Hubei Province, China in December 2019 as a pneumonia of unknown origin (Mahdy, 2020). As the world becomes increasingly interconnected, so do the risks we face. The COVID-19 pandemic has not stopped at national borders. It has affected people regardless of nationality, level of education, income, or gender. But the same has not been true for its consequences, which have hit the most vulnerable hardest (Schleicher, 2020).

On the other hand, the fact that we are facing a global health pandemic, the teachers still build knowledge and understanding in response to opportunities provided by the Department of Education (DepEd). Face-to-face learning engagement of students in the traditional classroom set-up has been suspended due to the Coronavirus disease otherwise known as the COVID-19 pandemic. As stated in DepEd Order No. 12 series. 2020 otherwise known as the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP), is a set of educational interventions designed to address the basic education challenges caused by COVID-19. The BE-LCP is one of the learning delivery modes used in Modular Distance Learning. In developing the BE-LCP, DepEd engaged internal and external stakeholders for inputs in the design of a learning delivery strategy and operational direction that ensures the health, safety, and well-being of all learners, teachers, and personnel of the Department. The BE-LCP stands on the following principles: a. Protect the health, safety, and well-being of learners, teachers, and personnel, and prevent the further transmission of COVID-19; b. Ensure learning continuity through K-12 curriculum adjustments, alignment of learning materials, deployment of multiple learning delivery modalities, provision of corresponding training for teachers and school leaders, and proper orientation of parents or guardians of learners; c. Facilitate the safe return of teaching and non-teaching personnel and learners to workplaces and schools/CLCs. taking

into consideration the scenarios projected by the Department of Health (DOH) and the Inter-Agency Task Force for the Management of Emerging Infectious Diseases in the Philippines (IATF). Complemented by other credible sources, and balanced with DepEd's risk assessments: d. Be sensitive to equity considerations and concerns, and endeavor to address them the best we can; and e. Link and bridge the BE-LCP to DepEd's pivot to quality and into the future of education, under the framework of Sulong EduKalidad and Futures Thinking in Education.

The BE-LCP is consistent with the mandate of Section 1, Article XIV of the 1987 Constitution for the state to protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels and take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all. Under Section 6, Chapter 1 of Republic Act No. 9155, or the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, DepEd is vested with the authority, accountability, and responsibility for ensuring access to, promoting equity in, and improving the quality of basic education.

Hence, the BE-LCP aims to ensure the health, safety, and well-being of the learners, teachers, and personnel in the time of COVID-19, while finding ways for education to continue amidst the crisis. In particular, the BE-LCP has been designed with a legal framework responsive to the "new normal," keeping in mind the constitutional mandate to uphold all citizens' right to quality education at all times.

Moreover, many educational reforms have emphasized the importance of good teaching that allows students to actively acquire knowledge. Introduction to Philosophy of the Human Person as one of the core Senior High School (SHS) subjects was not exempted from the various changes in the educational system. New learning styles and concepts, such as the use of modules, are being credited with encouraging students to learn independently, allowing them to critically think and communicate their ideas.

Besides, every student is entitled to a quality education. As a result, they strive, study hard, and persevere in their academics. The school, on the other hand, is a major factor influencing the quality of education. Fortunately, Philippine Investment Management, University of Pangasinan (PHINMA UPang) College Urdaneta Inc. provides quality education, knowledge enrichment, skill development, and the production of competent students. Since the pandemic began, some students have been concerned about how they will continue their education knowing that the situation will be difficult. Fortunately, PHINMA Education offered a Flexible Learning Program that allowed students to study at their own pace at home.

Flexible learning (FLEX Learning) is the learning modality (blended learning) that has been used since the beginning of classes at PHINMA UPang College Urdaneta, where the researcher is currently teaching. The Philippine PHINMA Education Flex Learning Program allows the creation of the following learning environments: 1. Gain knowledge from both distance and face-to-face sessions. 2. Attend face-to-face classes when it is safe to do so and when the government permits it. 3. Seek help from teachers via texts, phone calls, and social media. 4. Only take 6-8 subjects in one semester. Furthermore, this is the school's commitment to providing students with access to quality education regardless of their circumstances. Flex learning allows students to choose their path by giving them greater control over how, when, and where they learn and experience things, which can lead to better outcomes and greater academic success.

With the sudden shift in learning modality and its implementation in PHINMA-UPang College Urdaneta, Inc., the researcher became interested in conducting a study on the effectiveness of modular distance instruction as a tool to improve each learner's special aptitude and interest in appreciating Philosophy under FLEX Learning, which the researcher has been teaching for the past five years. The researcher saw the importance of investigating to improve student performance in this context.

2 Review of Related Literature

The spread of COVID-19 has sent shockwaves across the globe. While the long-term impact of the crisis is uncertain, the pandemic may affect public spending on education as funds are diverted into the health sector and the economy. Many universities and colleges worldwide suspended classroom teaching due to the novel coronavirus pandemic and switched to online teaching (Schleicher, 2020).

Furthermore, the teacher must assist the student's learning in the new normal education. This does not imply that the teacher 'spoon feeds' the students as if they were infants. It does imply that the teacher's priority should be to ensure that the students learn as much as possible. Learning modules and other supplementary materials would be extremely beneficial to students during this pandemic, but they must be carefully planned, taking into account the student's learning styles, language, and background. In short, teachers must be student-centered rather than teacher-centered.

The studies of Ali (2015), Lim (2016), Orines (2017), Vergara (2017), Moradi, Liu, Luchies, Patterson, and Darban (2018) are relevant to the current study because the researcher is also interested in the use of modules as self-instructional materials that come in the form of self-learning setups and are focused on interaction-centered activities. Various studies have focused on the idea that the main driving force behind modules in the teaching-learning process is that they have roles that can help solve key educational problems.

The research of Nunez (2017), Palisoc (2018), Leonardo (2018), and Yason (2018) focused on the students using interventions such as modules and supplementary materials to improve their performance. The said studies made use of experimental design where the two groups received different modes of instruction and found that the experimental group which made use of modules and interventions was noted to have significant improvement as evidenced by the results of the improved performance of the learners. The present study is guided by the findings of the research that learners regardless of their year level find modular instruction interesting and highly motivating.

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The researcher made use of the Quasi-Experimental Method using the two-group design. Both groups were pre-tested, and both were post-tested, the ultimate difference being that one group had undergone online distance instruction which was the control group. On the other hand, the other group was administered through modular distance instruction which was the experimental group.

To ascertain the significant difference that exists between the performance levels of two groups namely, the control group, (the group which is exposed to online distance instructions), and the experimental group, (the group exposed to modular distance instructions), a pre-test and post-test were administered by the researcher to both groups of learners.

3.2 Sources of Data

The subjects of the study were the 12 HUMSS students of PHINMA UPang College Urdaneta. The 12 HUMSS students were taken from the two sections of Grade 12 HUMSS learners that were handled by the researcher during the First Quarter of the First Semester, A.Y. 2021-2022. The researcher used the tossing of coins as a means to select who would be the Experimental and Control Groups. The Grade 12 HUMSS 2 was the control group exposed to online distance instruction. On the other hand, the 12 HUMSS 1 was the experimental group that will undergo modular distance instruction.

3.3 Statistical Treatment of Data

To identify the level of performance of the two groups of learners in Introduction to Philosophy of the Human Person, a pre-test and post-test were given to students. Computed mean and mean percentage scores were used to note the level of performance of the two groups in the pre-test and post-test results through comparative analysis of the scores of the two groups.

To determine if there is a significant difference in the performance level of the two groups of Grade 12 HUMSS learners in Introduction to Philosophy of the Human Person in the pre-test and post-test, a T-test for non-correlated data was used.

The t-test for correlated data was used in determining the significant difference in the pre-test and post-test within each of the two groups namely, the control group and experimental group.

4 Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

4.1 Performance of the Grade 12 Learners in Introduction to Philosophy of The Human Person as Revealed by the Pre-test Results

It could be observed from the table that both the control and experimental groups obtained are nearly identical means in the pre-test administered by the researcher. The table discloses that the control group obtained a mean score of 18.28 and a mean percentage score of 36.56. However, the experimental group obtained a mean of 18.96 and a mean percentage score of 37.92. Additionally, as to the mean percentage scores both groups obtained way below the DepEd's prescribed mastery of 75 %. It could be deduced that there is a need to improve the performance of the Grade 12 learners in Introduction to Philosophy of the Human Person.

Table 2. Pre-test Results of Control and Experimental Group in Grade 12 Introduction to Philosophy of the Human Person

Group	MEAN	Mean Percentage Score (MPS)
Control Group	18.28	36.56
Experimental Group	18.96	37.92

4.2 Significant Difference in the Performance of the Control and Experimental Group in the Pre-test

As to the significant difference in the performance of the control and experimental group in a pre-test, a t-test for independent groups or uncorrelated means was used. Table 3 presents the results of the study based on the analysis of data gathered.

Table 3. Test of Significance of the Difference in the Performance of the Control and Experimental Group in the Pre-test
N=50

Group	Mean	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	Significance	Decision
Control	18.28	0.68	0.378	Not Significant	Ho is Accepted
Experimental	18.96				

critical t-value = 2.011 at 0.5 df = 48

Looking intently at Table 3, it could be deduced that the learners registered a mean difference of 0.68. This would mean that there is an equal distribution of learners classified as heterogeneous groupings. The two groups are comparable before the start of the experiment.

It could be deduced that the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the performance of the two groups in the pre-test is accepted because the computed t-value of 0.378 is lesser than the critical t-value of 2.011 at 0.5 level of significance.

4.3 Performance of the Grade 12 learners in Introduction to Philosophy of The Human Person as revealed by the Post-test results

Table 4 shows that the learners in the control group obtained a mean score of 22.36 in Introduction to Philosophy of the Human Person. The Mean Percentage Score of this group exposed to online distance instruction is 44.72. However, the mean percentage score of 44.72 is below the standard set by the Department of Education. On the other hand, the experimental group obtained a mean score of 28.04 in the post-test in Introduction to Philosophy of the Human Person 12 and the t-computed mean percentage score is 56.08. This strengthens the claim of Vergara (2017) that the use of supplementary learning materials is encouraged particularly those that are developed by the facilitator to suit the local

needs and context. However, the the challenge is to produce contextualized learning modules that answer the needs of out-of-school youth and adults.

Table 4. Test of Significance of the Difference in the Performance of the Control and Experimental Group in the Pre-test
 N=50

Group	MEAN	Mean Percentage Score
Control Group	22.36	44.72
Experimental Group	28.04	56.08

4.4 Significant Difference in the Performance of the Control and Experimental Group in the Post-test

The table bears the comparison of the performances of the two groups of learners based on the post-test results in Introduction of the Human Person. Since the t-computed of 6.058 is greater than the critical value of 2.06 we can say that there is a significant improvement in the performance of the students after the use of Modular Distance Instruction. We can arrive at a similar analysis if we use a significant value that is less than 0.05.

Table 5. Test of Significance of the Difference in the Performance of the Control and Experimental Group in the Post-test
 N=50

Group	Mean	Mean difference	Computed t-value	Significance	Decision
Control	22.36	5.68	6.058	Significant	Ho is
Experimental	28.04				Rejected

Critical t-value = 2.064 at .05 df = 48

The findings of the study are also similar to the findings of Pasoquen (2015) that the use of the instructional module in teaching Grade 8 Physical Education improved the level of performance of the students, as a result, instructional materials like instructional modules are recommended to be utilized in Grade 8 Physical Education.

Looking intently at Table 6, it could be deduced that the learners registered a mean difference of 4.080. This would mean that there is an equal distribution of learners classified as heterogeneous groupings.

It can be gleaned from the table that there is an increase in the mean of the post-test of the students. This increase is considered significant since the t-computed value of 3.404 is greater than the critical value of 2.011. Moreover, this can also be verified using the significant value 0.002 which is less than 0.05. This means that there is a significant improvement in the performance of the students after the use of Online Distance Instruction.

Table 6. Test of Significant Difference in the Performance of the Control Group in the Pre-test and Post-Test
 N=25

Control Group	Mean	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	Significance	Decision
Pre-test	18.28	4.080	3.404	Significant	Ho is
Post-test	22.36				Rejected

critical t-value = 2.011 at 0.5 df = 24

These findings support the claim of Nardo, M.T.B (2017) that the use of modules encourages independent study. One of the benefits of using modules for instruction is the acquisition of better self-study or learning skills among students.

It also reinforces Leonardo's (2018) claim that using modules can foster a sense of responsibility in completing tasks. The students progress on their own with little or no help from the teacher. They are learning how to learn and are becoming more self-assured.

Table 7 shows the data on the pre-test and post-test of the experimental group exposed to modular distance instruction. Having a mean difference of 9.0840 and computed t-value of 6.058 which is higher than the critical value of 2.011 at 0.05 level of significance with the degree of freedom of 24. It can be deduced that the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the performance of the grade 12 learners in Introduction to Philosophy of the Human Person as exposed to modular distance instruction in the pre-test and post-test is hereby rejected. The rejection of the null hypothesis is based on the difference of the t-computed value from the critical value. This reflects that there was a significant improvement in the performance of this group in Introduction to Philosophy of the Human Person after they were exposed to modular distance instruction.

This supports the claim of Palisoc (2018) that the modular approach is a style of teaching and learning that is learner-centered considering that the student has to learn everything in the module through his effort at his chosen phase.

Table 7. Test of Significant Difference in the Performance of the Experimental Group in the Pre-test and Post-Test
 N=25

Experimental Group	Mean	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	Significance	Decision
Pre-test	18.96	9.08	6.058	Significant	Ho is
Post-test	28.04				Rejected

critical t-value = 2.011 at 0.5 df = 24

4.5 Performance of Grade 12 in Introduction to Philosophy of The Human Person

The mean gain obtained in the experimental group is 9.08 while the mean gain obtained in the control group is 4.08. It can be gleaned from the same table that the two groups obtained a mean difference of 5.000. Since t-computed 3.696 is greater than a critical value of 2.011, we can say that there is a significant difference between the performance of the experimental and the control group. Furthermore, we can say that the students in the experimental group performed better than those who were in the control group. The students have a significant improvement in the performance of 12 HUMSS1 after they were exposed to Modular Distance Instruction rather than Online Distance Instruction. The group mean percentage score of 56.08% is average based on the mastery level set and prescribed by the Department of Education.42

Table 8. Test of Significance of the Difference Between the Performance of the Control and Experimental Groups in Introduction to Philosophy of the Human Person

Group	Mean Gain	Mean diff.	T-value	Significant value	Decision
Control	4.08	5.000	3.696	0.013	Ho is rejected
Experimental	9.08				

Critical t-value = 2.011 at 0.5 level of significance = df = 48

This finding is similar to the findings of Roque (2019) because based on his study he found that there is a significant difference in the performance of the control and the experimental group in the post-test; the learners who were taught using the modular instruction (the experimental group) performed significantly better than the learners exposed to traditional instruction (the control group) and it is concluded that the modular instruction is an effective teaching approach that could be used in teaching Araling Panlipunan 7.

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

The performance of the control and experimental groups is low. There is a significant difference in the performance of the control and experimental groups as revealed in the post-test results. The performance of the experimental group is higher than the control group in the post-test results. There is a significant difference in the performance of the control and the experimental group in the post-test; the learners who were taught using the modular distance instruction (the experimental group) performed significantly better than the learners exposed to Online Distance Instruction (the control group) and it is concluded that the modular distance instruction is an effective teaching approach that could be used in teaching Grade 12 Introduction to Philosophy of the Human Person. The experimental group performed significantly better than the control group.

Teachers should utilize modular distance instruction in teaching Introduction to Philosophy of The Human Person. School administrators should encourage Introduction To Philosophy of The Human Person teachers to use modules as a teaching approach. Teachers must maximize the prescribed modules by the Department of Education to further confirm their effectiveness. Future researchers must conduct the same experiment to determine the effect of modular distance instruction in teaching Introduction to Philosophy of The Human Person to confirm the effectiveness of the use of modular distance instruction.

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